

The Lifting of Price Limits and the Stock Market Quality: The Case of the Taiwanese Stock Market

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Abstract: In order to increase the market efficiency and connect with the international stock market mechanism, the Taiwan Stock Exchange had published the price fluctuation limitations and relaxed the price fluctuation limits from 7% to 10% on June 1, 2015. Asian stock markets tend to have the least price limits relaxation, however, owing to the Taiwan stock market owns more retail investors, and retail investors tend to jump on the bandwagon when trading stocks. The purpose of this paper is to discuss the system modification on price limits and its influences on the stock market quality. The research would be conducted by evaluating the Taiwan stock market system to provide other researchers with a reference for future policy formulation.

Keywords: price limits, price variance, depth, trading volume, stock price volatility.

1. Introduction

The Global financial crisis was triggered in September 2008, as history repeated itself, the Black Monday when stock markets crashed internationally remained an unforgettable financial disaster for global investors. The global financial crisis aggravated the overreaction from the investors to the stock market which caused the global panic and the increase of market risks, finally led to bankrupts of a numerous number of businesses and financial institutions. The fall of these enterprise and financial institutions has brought a significant economic impact to the other countries and all these outcomes from the crisis

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have warned the world that people should be prudent and cautious to the stock markets.¹

For the sake of stabilization of the global stock markets and preventing excess volatility on the stock markets, stock exchanges from different countries would have to discuss whether the appropriate cooling-off effect on the excess volatility of the stock prices should be adopted. For instance, the circuit breaker mechanism in China and the price limits in Taiwan stock market where the supporters say the adequate cooling-off effect could enable the information to be exchanged fluently and reduce the information asymmetry (Christie, Corwin and Harris, 2002). Moreover, the investors could acquire reasonable market information and evaluate the real stock market price hence ease the volatility of stock markets (Greenwald and Stein, 1988 and 1991). Opponents argue that the cooling effect may influence the reaction of the day of stock market's trading information, slowing down the ability in identifying the stock price, reducing the price efficiency of the market, thus it will bring the side effect to the market price. Due to the fluctuation of the price limits and the inconsistency of the stock price increase, it causes the investors become panic and keep following up the stock trades, in resulting of high volatility on the stock prices that negatively impact the market liquidity and price efficiency (Amihud and Mendelson, 1987 and 1991; Gerety and Mulherin, 1992) and increase the volatility of the market (Lee, Ready and Seguin, 1994; Kim and Rhee, 1997). From the above, it can be known that the effect of cooling-off effect seems to change in depending on the empirical objects and research period.

Countries had relaxed the price limits in order to eventually connect with the international market. The relaxation of price limits in Taiwan was adjusted from 7% to 10% since June 2015. However, owing to the Taiwan stock market holds more retail investors and they tend to jump on the bandwagon when trading stocks. The report would evaluate the price limits relaxation in Taiwan and its impact on stock market quality to provide a sophisticated reference for future implementation of relevant trading policy.

The structure of the report would be as follows: Chapter 2 describes data and variable measurement; Chapter 3 highlights methodology; Chapter 4 discusses results and finally Chapter 5 gives conclusions

2. Data and Variable Measurement

2.1. Data

The main variables used in this study includes price variables, depth, volatility, relative

¹The price limits in Korea is planning to increase to 30%, Japan would control the price limits in between 14%-30%, the price limits in Thailand and Malaysia are 30% and Hong Kong has no price limits.

trading volume, stock price and market value. All the data were adopted from the Taiwan Economic Journal (TEJ). The research period was between January 1, 2015 to December 31, 2015. Owing to the date of the price limits relaxation was June 1, 2015; therefore, the prior research period was set between January 1, 2015, and May 30, 2015, and later research period would be June 1, 2015, to December 31, 2015. The research objects include all listed companies (The delisted companies during research period were eliminated from the research objects).

2.2. Variable Measurement

The variable measurement is given as follows:

$$\text{Spread}_{i,t} = ((\text{Ask}_{i,t} - \text{Bid}_{i,t}) / (\text{Ask}_{i,t} + \text{Bid}_{i,t})) * 100 \tag{1}$$

$$\text{Depth}_{i,t} = Q_{\text{bid},i,t} + Q_{\text{ask},i,t} \tag{2}$$

$$\text{TR1}_{i,t} = V_{i,t} / O_{i,t} \tag{3}$$

$$\sigma_{i,t} = (\ln(P_{i,t,h} / P_{i,t,l}))^2 / 4 \ln 2^{0.5} \times 100 \tag{4}$$

$\text{Bid}_{i,t}$ ($\text{Ask}_{i,t}$) is the company i's the t day's best buying (selling) quotation before market close; $Q_{\text{bid},i,t}$ ($Q_{\text{ask},i,t}$) represents the company i's the t day's best buying (selling) quotation volume; $P_{i,t}$ would be company i the t day's strike price. TRI means company i the t day's turnover rate; V represents the traded shares; O would be the outstanding stocks and $P_{i,t,h}$ ($P_{i,t,l}$) indicates the company I the t day's the highest (lowest) trading price.

3. Empirical Results

3.1. Summary Statistics

In Table 1, we conclude that the daily average trading volume in this period was 2350 with a standard deviation of 7279; the average turnover rate was 44.57% and the standard deviation was about 86%; and the average number of outstanding shares was 787627 shares. The standard deviation is 2080395; the average market capitalization is 29972 million dollars, the standard deviation is 149061 million, the average number of transactions is 884.6253 shares, the standard deviation is 1771 shares; the average rate of return is -5.59%, the standard deviation is 2.3158 %.

Trading volume is positively correlated and turnover rate, the number of floating shares, market capitalization, turnover pen number and the return rate, i.e., the larger the trading volume, the greater the market value. Turnover is positively correlated with the rate of return. The turnover rate is negatively correlated with the number of shares and the market capitalization, i.e., the larger the turnover ratio indicates the smaller the number of shares and the smaller market capitalization. The number of shares traded in the market is positively correlated with the market value and the number of transactions. The number of outstanding shares is negatively correlated with the rate of return while the market value is positively correlated with the stock return.

Table 1: Summary Statistics

	TV(1000 lots)	Turnover	OUPS (1000 lots)	MV(Million dollars)	Trades (lot)	Return
Mean	2350	0.4457	787627	29972	884.6253	-0.0559
Stdev	7279	0.86	2080395	149061	1771	2.3158
Max	278922	29.715	25930380	4006179	53957	66.4976
Min	0	0	20314	138	0	-260.368
TV	1					
Turnover	0.2550***	1				
OUPS	0.6295***	-0.0648***	1			
MV	0.3480***	-0.0317***	0.6964***	1		
Trades	0.8813***	0.4018***	0.6248***	0.4572***	1	
Returns	0.0344***	0.1158***	-0.0001	0.0040*	0.0314***	1

Note: *, ** and *** indicate significance level at 10%, 5% and 1%. This table presents the following variables, including the Outstanding share(OUPS), Turnover rate (Turnover), Trading volume (TV), Market Value (MV) , Number of Trades(Trades), Return. The summary statistics includes the following variables: the average (Mean), standard deviation (Stdev), Maximum value (Max) and Minimum value (Min). The data study period is from 2015/01/01 to 2015/12/31.

3.2. The Impact of Lifting of Price Limit on the Market Quality

In Table 2, Panel A discusses the effect of price limit on the spread. The result showed a significant decrease as the trading time approaches the closing (spread was 0.2405% at the pre-period open time and 0.2146% at the pre-period time, while the average spread was -0.7081% and -1.6942% for the pre-period (post-period), respectively). The difference between the pre-period and post-period is significantly different from 0. In Panel B, The result shows that as the closing time approaches, the depth increases temporarily (the depth is 2307.6851 (thousand shares) at the opening period while the depth is 3924.9860 (thousand shares) at the closing period. Over the post-period, the depth is 1586.7982 (thousands) at the market opening, while depth is 2679.5851 (thousands) at the market closing). In Panel C, the trading volume rise sharply as the closing time approaches (the trading volume at the opening was 0.0119 million shares and the trading volume at the close was 0.0171 million shares). The trading volume of the latter period increases as the market approaches closing. As trading passed by (trading volume at the opening was 0.0138 million and the trading volume at the close was 0.0181 million), the difference is significantly different from 0. Finally, we discuss the effect of the price limit on the opening, closing, and the stock price fluctuations (Panel D). As a result, the stock price fluctuate significantly as the time approaches the closing time (13.1397% at the market open and 12.5344% at the market close; the variation of stock price 15.7487% while price volatility at market closing is 15.5755%), the difference is significantly different from 0.

Table 2: Effect of Lifting of Price limit on the Intraday Pattern of Market Quality

	1(9:00-9:30)	2(9::30-10:00)	3(10:00-10:30)	4(10:30-11:00)	5(11:00-11:30)	6(11:30-12:00)	7(12:00-12:30)	8(12:30-13:00)	9(13:00-13:30)
Panel A: Spread (%)									
Pre	0.2405***	0.2242***	0.2184 ***	0.2061***	0.2158***	0.2136***	0.2076***	0.2095***	0.2146***
Post	-0.7081***	-0.9624***	-2.8835***	-2.0166***	-2.0701***	-1.7462***	-1.6601***	-1.6942***	-1.8236***
Diff	0.9486***	1.1866***	3.1019***	2.2227***	2.2858***	1.9598***	1.8677***	1.9037***	2.0382***
Panel B: Depth (1000 lots)									
Pre	2307.6851***	3118.2609***	3453.2763***	3746.0342***	3996.1424***	4054.7260***	4140.2700***	4239.4550***	3924.9860***
Post	1586.7982***	2034.8458***	2252.1618***	2453.7603***	2529.3231***	2619.7472***	2728.5413***	2748.3510***	2679.5851***
Diff	720.8868***	1083.4151***	1201.1145***	1292.2739***	1466.8193***	1434.9788***	1411.7287***	1491.1040***	1245.4009***
Panel C: Vol (million dollars)									
Pre	0.0119***	0.0128***	0.0142***	0.0137***	0.0148***	0.0159***	0.0160***	0.0171***	0.0218***
Post	0.0138***	0.0149***	0.0159***	0.0148***	0.0167***	0.0179***	0.0172***	0.0181***	0.0165
Diff	-0.0019***	-0.0021***	-0.0017***	-0.0011**	-0.0019***	-0.0020***	-0.0012	-0.001	0.0054***
Panel D: σ (%)									
Pre	13.1397***	13.0285***	12.9341***	12.8439***	12.8537***	12.7946***	12.7525***	12.6708***	12.5344***
Post	15.7487***	15.6729***	15.9256***	15.7895***	15.8234***	15.7002***	15.6541***	15.5755***	15.2442***
Diff	-2.6090***	-2.6444***	-2.9915***	-2.9456***	-2.9697***	-2.9056***	-2.9016***	-2.9048***	-2.7098***

Note: *, ** and *** indicate significance level at 10%, 5% and 1%. This table describes the effect of lifting of price limit on the intraday pattern of market quality. Panel A indicates the mean value of the spread (Spread) for the Pre-(Post-) period for each sub-period. Panel B indicates the mean value of the depth (Depth) for the Pre-(Post-) period for each sub-period. Panel C indicates the mean value of the trading volume (Vol) for the Pre-(Post-) period for each sub-period. Panel D indicates the mean value of the Volatility (σ) for the Pre-(Post-) period. Diff indicates the difference between the pre-period and post-period. The pre-period (Pre-) is from 2015/01/01 to 2015/05/30 while the post-period (Post-) is from 2015/06/01 to 2015/12/31.

4. Conclusions

The purpose of this study is to explore the effect of the lifting of price limit on the stock market in order to maintain the trading rules. The Taiwan stock market lifts the price limit from 7% to 10% on 2015/06/01. This study is expected to explore the effect of the lifting of the price limit on the market quality. Empirical results showed that after the relaxation of the price limit, the spread, trading volume and the volatility increases significantly while the depth decreases significantly. It shows that the lifting of price limit will have a certain effect on the market quality.

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